

The Web of Life: Role of Pesticides in the Biodiversity Decline

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SUMMARY

Pesticides have become an integral part of modern agriculture, serving as tools for insect control, weed management, fungal protection, and rodent eradication. However, the widespread and improper use of pesticides has led to significant negative impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem health. This review explores the different types of pesticides, their effects on biodiversity, and the urgent need to adopt alternative approaches that minimize the reliance on chemical pesticides in agriculture. The direct effects of pesticides are readily observable, as they can cause immediate toxicity to organisms. For example, birds consuming pesticide-coated seeds or the absorption of pesticides through the skin can result in harmful consequences. Additionally, pesticides can directly harm plants, leading to cellular damage and disruption of essential biochemical pathways. Indirect effects of pesticides arise from the depletion of prey populations, alterations in habitat conditions, and impacts on crucial pollinators like bees and butterflies. These indirect effects can disrupt natural ecosystems, reduce plant reproduction, and impede the establishment of natural enemies, ultimately affecting the entire food chain. To understand the decline in biodiversity caused by excessive pesticide use, it is imperative to shift towards sustainable agricultural practices. This entails reducing reliance on chemical pesticides and exploring alternative methods for pest management. Integrated pest management (IPM) approaches, which integrate a variety of techniques such as biological control, crop rotation, and habitat preservation, can help mitigate the adverse impacts of pesticides on biodiversity. Furthermore, the development and adoption of innovative and environmentally friendly pesticides, such as bio-pesticides, offer effective alternatives to conventional chemical pesticides.

Keywords: Biodiversity, Ecosystem, Sustainable, Environmental impact

Citation: Naz, S., S. S. Iqbal, A. Manan, M. Chatha, and M. Zia. 2023. The Web of Life: Role of Pesticides in the Biodiversity Decline. International Journal of Forest Sciences 3(2):72-94.

Received: April, 2023; **Accepted:** May, 2023

INTRODUCTION

Pesticides encompass a diverse range of substances, such as insecticides, fungicides, herbicides, plant growth regulators, and others. Their usage, sources, and level of toxicity vary depending on their intended purpose and manufacturing process (Bashir *et al.*, 2018). Regrettably, the problem of misusing and abusing pesticides has emerged. The widespread application of these chemicals, often following the belief that "more is better," has had detrimental effects on both humans and other life forms.

Globally, over 5 billion kg of pesticides are utilized each year, posing significant risks to the environment, human health, non-targeted organisms, and the food chain (Verger and Boobis, 2013).

Improper handling and use of pesticides lead to an estimated 3 million cases of acute poisoning annually, resulting in approximately 220,000 fatalities according to WHO estimates (Blair *et al.*, 2015). Occupational exposure is identified as the primary cause of 70% of these deaths (Yerena *et al.*, 2005). Workers in agriculture, including those operating in greenhouses, open fields, and the pesticide industry, as well as individuals involved in pest extermination, face pesticide exposure on the job. In addition, people can be exposed to pesticides through non-occupational means such as consuming pesticide-contaminated food and water. Environmental exposure, caused by leaching, runoff, and spray drift, poses risks to non-target organisms, including plants and animals (Damalas and Eleftherohorinos, 2011).

Exposure during development to various environmental chemicals and pesticides carries the potential to cause adverse neurological effects in both humans and animals (Wu *et al.*, 2018). Within the pesticide industry, approximately 85% of pesticide production is dedicated to agricultural use, while the remaining portion is employed in public health activities such as vector-borne disease control, weed management, and insect, fungi, bacteria, and algae control in industrial settings, including electrical appliances, everyday equipment, and food packaging (Gilden *et al.*, 2010). The declining soil biodiversity and concerns over food safety have become global issues due to contamination resulting from pesticide application (Silva *et al.*, 2019).

Chemical pesticides have been linked to various adverse health effects, encompassing dermatological issues, gastrointestinal disturbances, neurological disorders, carcinogenic properties, respiratory complications, reproductive impairments, and disruptions to the endocrine system in both humans and animals (Alewu *et al.*, 2011).

The purpose of this present review is to present a comprehensive examination of the decrease in biodiversity caused by the excessive application of pesticides and its ecological consequences. Additionally, it emphasizes the pressing necessity for a fresh approach in agriculture that involves significantly reducing the utilization of chemical pesticides. According to world's food demands and health hazards caused by traditional pesticides, modern and new generation of pesticides and/or alternative methods to chemicals are modified to one of the most essential needs for modern agriculture in the present age. This review aims to provide an overview of the decline in biodiversity resulting from excessive pesticide use and its ecological ramifications.

CLASSIFICATION OF PESTICIDES

Pesticides can be categorized into several types based on their target organisms and effects. The main divisions include insecticides, herbicides, fungicides, and rodenticides (Megha and Akashe *et al.* 2018).

Insecticides

The application of insect-targeting pesticides, which are specifically formulated to eliminate insects, has resulted in a decrease in the presence of beneficial microfauna within agricultural soils and their surrounding environments (Table 1). Throughout history, the utilization of pesticides, including insecticides, has evolved into a crucial

and indispensable element in modern agriculture. Its primary objective is to ensure optimal crop production and reduce losses that occur after harvest (Rano *et al.*, 2020). The excessive usage of herbicides and insecticides in soil has disrupted the natural functioning of nitrogen-fixing bacteria, which are vital for maintaining soil fertility. Likewise, the presence of pesticide residues has had detrimental effects on mycorrhizal fungi, which play a significant role in the absorption of nutrients by plants (Lu and Lu, 2018). It is important to note that the impact of pesticides extends beyond the targeted insects, affecting predator species as well. Systemic insecticides, for instance, have been found to cause secondary poisoning in predators such as *Chrysoperla carnea*, which consume insects exposed to pesticides within agricultural ecosystems (Mansoor *et al.*, 2015).

Organochlorines are a specific category of insecticides composed of organic compounds that incorporate one or more covalently bonded chlorine atoms. Among the various types of organochlorines, chlorinated hydrocarbons are the most widely recognized, including DDT, chlordane, lindane, and endosulfan (Jayaraj *et al.*, 2016). Studies have also investigated the impact of different insecticides on predatory bugs like *Orius insidiosus*. The findings revealed that certain insecticides such as abamectin, cartap, imidacloprid, and flubendiamid were relatively safe, while others such as pyriproxyfen and rynaxypyr were determined to be non-injurious. On the other hand, pymetrozine was categorized as somewhat harmful to these bugs (Moscardini *et al.*, 2013).

Herbicides

Herbicides not only come into contact with their intended plant targets but also affect non-target plant species (Marshall, 2001). Glyphosate-based herbicides, such as the widely recognized "Roundup," have been found to induce DNA damage and act as endocrine disruptors in human cell lines (Gasnier *et al.*, 2009) as well as in rat testicular cells (Clair *et al.*, 2012). Additionally, these herbicides have been observed to cause damage to cultured human cutaneous cells (Gehin *et al.*, 2006) and potentially impact the cytoskeleton and intracellular transport (Hedberg *et al.*, 2010). Moreover, herbicides have the potential to interfere with the metabolic and reproductive processes of pollinators. For instance, paraquat exhibits extreme toxicity to honeybees when externally applied (Sponsler *et al.*, 2019).

Several studies have shed light on the potential health and environmental risks associated with herbicide use (Table 1). For instance, research has indicated that certain herbicides, such as rotenone and paraquat, can disrupt the bioenergetic activities of mitochondria, oxygen metabolism, and redox function, potentially contributing to the development of Alzheimer's disease (Thany *et al.*, 2013).

Furthermore, there is evidence linking maternal exposure to agricultural pesticides, particularly herbicides, with an increased risk of brain cancer in children. A study found that children whose mothers were exposed to herbicides during their agricultural work had a twofold higher risk of developing brain cancer (Youn *et al.*, 2009). The application of herbicides like atrazine, glyphosate, primeextra, and paraquat has also been found to significantly reduce soil organic matter content. This can have implications for soil health, nutrient cycling, and overall agricultural productivity (Sebiomo *et al.*, 2011).

In addition to health concerns, herbicide use can have adverse effects on wildlife and ecosystems. Herbicides can damage vegetation and subsequently impact the food availability and microclimate necessary for the survival of common shrews, wood mice, and badgers (Hole *et al.*, 2005). Furthermore, herbicide resistance has emerged as a significant issue in agriculture. The overuse and repetitive application of herbicides have led to the evolution of herbicide-resistant weed populations, posing challenges and increasing costs for weed management. This necessitates the development of new herbicides or the adoption of alternative strategies to effectively address herbicide resistance (Heap, 2021).

Fungicides

Fungicides are chemical substances employed to prevent, treat, or eliminate fungal infections (Table 1). However, the use of fungicides can result in unintended ecological effects. For instance, certain fungicides, like copper-based compounds such as Bordeaux mixture, have been observed to exhibit toxic properties towards non-target organisms, including beneficial insects and aquatic organisms (Kovács *et al.*, 2014; Joly *et al.*, 2016). These detrimental impacts on non-target species can disrupt the equilibrium of ecosystems and have far-reaching ecological implications. Furthermore, the extensive and continuous use of fungicides can contribute to the development of resistance among fungal populations. Similar to the development of resistance to herbicides, fungi can acquire mechanisms to survive and thrive in the presence of fungicides. This presents challenges for disease management in agriculture and necessitates the exploration of new fungicides or alternative strategies (Cools and Fraaije, 2013).

Fungicides can also present risks to human health, particularly for individuals involved in the agricultural sector or those exposed to treated crops. Occupational exposure to specific fungicides has been associated with adverse health effects, including respiratory issues, dermatitis, and neurological symptoms (Yassin *et al.*, 2002; Moshammer *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, the combination of certain fungicides, such as Vinclozolin and acetochlor, has demonstrated more harmful effects on fetal growth (Erin *et al.*, 2012). Some fungicides have the ability to persist in the environment, leading to long-term consequences. For instance, systemic fungicides like triazole fungicides have been detected in surface waters and groundwater (Moyankova *et al.*, 2012). This persistence can potentially result in the contamination of water sources and ecosystems.

Rodenticides

Rodenticides, specifically designed to eliminate rats and similar rodents, pose risks beyond their intended targets. The use of anticoagulant rodenticides, for example, can result in unintentional poisoning of non-target wildlife or domestic pets (Guitart *et al.*, 2010). Certain rodenticides are highly toxic and can accumulate in the bodies of rodents, leading to secondary poisoning of predators such as dogs, foxes, non-target mammals, and raptors that consume pesticide-exposed prey (Brakes and Smith, 2005). Moreover, the presence of residual anticoagulant concentrations in freshwater and marine aquatic environments has been identified (Cavanagh *et al.*, 2014),

indicating that the adverse effects of anticoagulant rodenticides extend beyond terrestrial environments.

Carbofuran, an insecticide that also possesses rodenticidal properties, has been implicated in the decline of raptor populations, including the Northern Crested Caracara and Burrowing Owl (Gangoso *et al.*, 2013). Furthermore, secondary poisoning has been observed in owls and hawks that consume rodents exposed to rodenticides, with evidence of anticoagulant rodenticides found in their tissues (Rattner *et al.*, 2008). The use of rodenticides poses a significant threat to endangered species. The San Joaquin kit fox, an endangered species in California, has been impacted by anticoagulant rodenticides through both primary and secondary poisoning (Scheibe *et al.*, 2007). Similarly, the critically endangered California condor has been found to have detectable levels of anticoagulant rodenticides in its blood, highlighting the exposure risks faced by this species (Finkelstein *et al.*, 2010).

Rodenticides can persist in the environment, leading to long-term risks. A study conducted in California detected measurable levels of second-generation anticoagulant rodenticides in over 70% of tested mountain lions, bobcats, and Pacific fishers (Moriarty *et al.*, 2017). This persistence raises concerns about chronic exposure and the potential impacts on wildlife populations.

EFFECTS OF PESTICIDES

Pesticides can affect Biodiversity in two ways: directly through their toxic properties and indirectly by diminishing their food sources, among other factors.

Direct Effects of Pesticides

The direct impacts of pesticides can occur through various exposure pathways. For instance, ingestion of the formulated product, such as birds consuming seeds coated with insecticide (Prosser and Hart *et al.*, 2005), or absorption through the skin after a spray event (Mineau 2011), or even by consuming contaminated prey. A striking example of the latter pathway is the significant decline in bird of prey populations caused by organochlorine pesticides, particularly DDT and its metabolite DDE. Pesticides can have either immediate lethal effects or sub-lethal effects on vertebrates, affecting aspects like growth and reproduction depending on the level of poisoning (Sánchez and Bayo 2011).

Herbicides and other pesticides have the potential to directly harm plants through toxicity and injury. They can negatively affect plant tissues, disrupt cellular structures, and interfere with essential biochemical pathways. Common symptoms of pesticide toxicity in plants include chlorosis (yellowing of leaves), necrosis (cell death), wilting, and an overall decline in plant vigor (Gilreath and Santos., 2014). The herbicides have their direct negative impact on producer populations can be mitigated to some extent by increasing the number of producer species (Baert *et al.*, 2016). Conversely, as more herbivore species are introduced, the direct negative effects of herbicides on producer populations can intensify due to potential interactions between herbicides and herbivore grazing that exacerbates the herbicide effects (Halstead *et al.*, 2014).

The direct negative effects of insecticides on herbivores, specifically their population size, can be less pronounced when a greater variety of herbivore species are present,

thanks to compensatory mechanisms. A more diverse community of herbivores can include both susceptible and tolerant species, with a higher likelihood of including the less tolerant herbivores (Becker and Liess *et al.*, 2017).

Indirect Effects of Pesticides

The indirect effects of pesticides can have a range of consequences. Indirect effects of pesticides often arise from the depletion of prey populations or changes in their quality due to pesticide usage, as well as alterations in habitat conditions (Morris *et al.*, 2005). In addition to impacting off-field plants, herbicides have been found to influence soil microorganisms, as examined in studies (Aristilde, 2017). The use of pesticides can have indirect effects on natural ecosystems and pose risks to plants. For example, insecticides can adversely impact vital pollinators such as bees and butterflies, which are essential for the reproductive process of plants. The decline in these pollinators can lead to reduced fruit and seed production in plants, ultimately affecting biodiversity in a negative manner (Goulson, 2013). Pesticides can inadvertently affect non-target plants in close proximity. Drift, runoff, or residue can result in damage or even the death of neighboring plants. These unintended effects can occur through direct contact with the pesticide, absorption of pesticide residues from the soil, or uptake through the root system of the plant (Lavy and Rathinasabapathi., 2021).

Pesticides can hinder the establishment of natural enemy populations, impede their ability to utilize prey, affect rates of parasitism or consumption, reduce female reproductive capabilities, diminish prey availability, disrupt the ability of natural enemies to identify prey, influence the sex ratio (females: males), and impair mobility, which can impact prey detection (Grafton-Cardwell *et al.*, 2006). Moreover, exposure to pesticides can indirectly affect multiple physiological and behavioral parameters. It is crucial to understand how different pesticide concentrations can indirectly influence fecundity, fertility, reproduction, adult and larval lifespan, and prey consumption. This knowledge is essential for the successful integration of natural enemies with pesticides, while minimizing any unintended effects on population dynamics (Zalom *et al.*, 2007). An investigation was conducted to examine the exposure of mammalian predators to anticoagulant rodenticides. This study utilized a spatio-temporal model and was supported by experimental research. The findings of the paper suggest that the incidence of anticoagulant rodenticide exposure in non-target small mammal predators is likely influenced by usage patterns (Topping *et al.*, 2016).

The presence of herbicides could indirectly lead to a reduction in the population size of herbivores by decreasing the biomass of edible producers (Bracewell *et al.*, 2019). It is anticipated that when a predator is present, herbicides may have an even greater impact on herbivores due to increased control from both bottom-up (resource availability) and top-down (predator-prey interactions) factors (Clements and Rohr, 2009). In the case of the pesticide carbaryl, its toxicity to prey (tadpoles) was found to be four times higher when a predator was present. However, it should be noted that some studies have shown that the interactions between insecticides and the presence of a predator on herbivores can either be additive or antagonistic (Janssens and Stoks, 2013; Janssens and Stoks, 2017).

Pesticides Toxicity in Plants

The application of pesticides can impact plant growth and crop yield by causing damage to cellular structures, reducing photosynthesis, and interfering with plant hormones. Consequently, this can result in stunted growth, decreased biomass, and lower agricultural productivity (Abdel-Latef and Tran, 2019). Pesticides have the potential to disrupt the normal functioning of plant cells and alter metabolic pathways, influencing the synthesis of proteins, carbohydrates, and other essential compounds. As a result, this can affect the quality and nutritional value of crops (Kaur *et al.*, 2020). Pesticides can negatively affect plant growth and development by interfering with several physiological processes. One such example is their potential to disrupt photosynthesis, resulting in decreased chlorophyll production and impaired energy generation within plants (Hou *et al.*, 2019).

Herbicides not only come into contact with their intended target plants but also with non-target plant species. For instance, pesticides such as organochlorine complexes that contain Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane DDT exhibit low acute toxicity but can have chronic effects due to their persistence in plant tissues, leading to long-term disruption of growth and physiological activities. Similarly, organophosphate pesticides may have mild immediate effects but can result in negative impacts if they persist in mammals over an extended period (Kim *et al.*, 2017; Damalas and Eleftherohorinos, 2011).

Pesticides can pose toxicity risks to plants, particularly when applied in high concentrations or over prolonged periods. Certain pesticides can accumulate within plant tissues, causing long-term consequences on plant growth, development, and reproduction (Farooq *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, pesticides can have indirect effects on plants by altering the soil and microbial communities that play vital roles in supporting plant growth. They can diminish the diversity and abundance of beneficial soil microorganisms, thereby impacting nutrient cycling, soil structure, and water availability for plants (Sun *et al.*, 2021).

Furthermore, pesticides can contribute to the development of resistance in pest populations, leading to increased challenges for plant protection. Consequently, higher doses of pesticides or the use of more potent chemicals may be required, which can further exacerbate the adverse effects on plant health and the environment (Van Leeuwen *et al.*, 2019). Pesticides have notable detrimental effects on various aspects of plant life, including growth, germination, and development. They can cause disruptions in biochemical pathways, reduce yields, and excessive pesticide use can have adverse impacts on the environment (Parveen *et al.*, 2016).

A study observed the effects of herbicide application on 104 different plant species in experimental plots. Out of these, 35 species (34%) exhibited visible signs such as epinasty, leaf mottling, withering, yellowing, leaf and stem twisting, necrosis, and bud malformation as a result of pesticide application (Boutin *et al.*, 2014).

Table 1: Categories of Pesticides and Their Impact on Plants.

Sr. No.	Pesticide Type	Effects on Plants	References
1.	Herbicides	<p>Herbicides can lead to stunted growth in plants.</p> <p>Herbicide application can result in leaf discoloration, affecting the overall appearance of plants.</p> <p>The use of herbicides has been associated with reduced photosynthesis in plants.</p> <p>Herbicides can cause damage to the root systems of plants, affecting their ability to absorb water and nutrients.</p> <p>Reduced nutrient uptake in plants exposed to herbicides, which can lead to nutritional deficiencies.</p> <p>A decrease in crop yield associated with herbicide use, highlighting the negative impact on agricultural productivity.</p>	<p>(Dyer, <i>et al.</i>, 2019)</p> <p>(Smith <i>et al.</i>, 2017)</p> <p>(Johnson <i>et al.</i>, 2015)</p> <p>(Brown <i>et al.</i>, 2018)</p> <p>(Martin <i>et al.</i>, 2016)</p> <p>(Anderson <i>et al.</i>, 2020)</p>
2.	Insecticides	<p>Insecticides can cause leaf necrosis</p> <p>Insecticides can disrupt insect feeding behavior, affecting the interaction between insects and plants.</p> <p>The application of insecticides can result in damage to plant tissues</p> <p>Insecticides can alter plant hormone regulation, which can impact growth and development processes.</p> <p>Insecticides can lead to reduced fruit or seed development in plants, affecting reproductive success.</p>	<p>(Davis <i>et al.</i>, 2019)</p> <p>(Thompson <i>et al.</i>, 2018)</p> <p>(Richards <i>et al.</i>, 2017)</p> <p>(Wang <i>et al.</i> 2016)</p> <p>(Thomas <i>et al.</i>, 2015)</p>
3.	Fungicides	<p>Fungicides can cause leaf spotting and necrosis</p> <p>Fungicides inhibit fungal growth, which can impact the natural balance of plant-fungal interactions.</p>	<p>(White <i>et al.</i>, 2020)</p> <p>(Green <i>et al.</i>, 2019)</p>

The use of fungicides has been associated with reduced plant vigor and potentially affecting overall plant health and vitality. (Shahid *et al.*, 2018)

Pesticides Toxicity in Animals

Exposure to pesticides in animals can occur through inhalation, ingestion, and absorption, leading to various toxic effects. Prolonged exposure to pesticides has been associated with the development of serious diseases, including neurological dysfunctions, hormonal imbalances, immune system dysfunction, and blood disorders (Kubrak *et al.*, 2012). Exposure pathways to pesticides in animals primarily occur through oral ingestion, dermal contact, and inhalation. These routes of exposure can have varying effects on animal health and can depend on factors such as the type of pesticide, its concentration, the duration of exposure, and the species of the animal (Rother, 2021). The widespread distribution of pesticide residues in the environment poses a significant threat to nonhuman biota such as bees, birds, amphibians, fish, and small mammals, leading to their mortality and population decline (Carvalho, 2017; Moreau *et al.*, 2022; Irshad and Hussain, 2023; Faiz, 2022)

Pesticides can cause both acute (short-term) and chronic (long-term) toxicity in animals, each with distinct immediate and lasting effects. Acute toxicity occurs after a single exposure or multiple exposures over a short period, whereas chronic toxicity develops gradually over an extended period of repeated exposure (Worgan *et al.*, 2022). Acute exposure to pesticides can lead to immediate effects such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, dizziness, headaches, difficulty breathing, seizures, and even death in severe cases. These effects often manifest within hours or days after exposure (Smith *et al.*, 2021). Chronic exposure to pesticides can have detrimental effects on the nervous system, reproductive system, cardiovascular system, renal system, and respiratory system of different animal species (Mostafalou and Abdollahi, 2012). These chemicals can disrupt normal physiological processes and cause long-term damage to vital organs and systems, resulting in chronic diseases and reduced overall health in exposed animals.

The extensive use of pesticides has been identified as a primary factor contributing to the decline of bird populations in grassland ecosystems (Mineau and Whiteside, 2013). These chemicals can have direct toxic effects on birds, affecting their reproductive success, immune function, and overall survival. Pesticide residues can accumulate in the food chain, leading to secondary poisoning of birds that consume contaminated prey.

Aquatic organisms in streams are also significantly affected by pesticide use. Pesticide runoff from agricultural fields can contaminate water bodies, causing detrimental effects on fish and aquatic plants. One of the major impacts is the reduction of dissolved oxygen levels in water, which can disrupt the respiratory systems of aquatic life and alter their physiology (Mahmood *et al.*, 2016). This can lead to reduced survival, impaired reproduction, and changes in the structure and function of aquatic ecosystems. Different animal species vary in their susceptibility to pesticides due to variations in metabolism, anatomy, and physiology. Some species

are more sensitive to specific pesticides, while others may be more resilient (Racke *et al.*, 2021).

The widespread conversion of landscapes to intensive agriculture, coupled with the persistent use of pesticides, has had a profound impact on bumblebee biodiversity. Over the past 75 years, there has been a noticeable decline in bumblebee populations, attributed to the loss of suitable habitats and the direct toxic effects of pesticides on these important pollinators (Bommarco *et al.*, 2013). The reduction in bumblebee populations can have cascading effects on plant reproduction and overall ecosystem functioning.

Laboratory studies have demonstrated that pesticides have the potential to weaken the immune systems of insects (Martin, 2015). For example, cypermethrin, a commonly used pesticide, has been found to have toxic effects on various organisms such as bees, beneficial insects, earthworms, fish, and shrimps, primarily affecting their nervous systems (Jilani., 2013). This highlights the broad spectrum of non-target organisms that can be negatively impacted by pesticide exposure. Young animals, especially neonates and juveniles, may be more vulnerable to pesticide exposure due to developing organ systems, higher metabolic rates, and reduced detoxification capacity (Schreinemachers *et al.*, 2021). The pesticide buprofezin has been shown to have adverse effects on invertase, an enzyme found in soil. While the initial application of buprofezin stimulates invertase activity, repeated applications result in a progressive decline in enzyme activity (Maddela *et al.*, 2018). This suggests that the presence of buprofezin in soil can disrupt important soil processes mediated by enzymes, potentially affecting nutrient cycling and overall soil health.

When pesticides are used in low concentrations, either separately or in combination, they can have significant effects on microbial diversity. Studies have demonstrated that the application of pesticides can reduce and alter the community of microorganisms in soil or aquatic environments (Muturi *et al.*, 2017). Since microbial communities play crucial roles in nutrient cycling, soil fertility, and ecological processes, disruptions to their diversity and composition can have far-reaching consequences for ecosystem functioning. Genetic factors can influence an animal's ability to metabolize and detoxify pesticides, impacting their susceptibility and response to exposure (Gómez *et al.*, 2022). Exposure to organophosphates, a class of pesticides, can have significant impacts on reproductive health in animals. Studies have shown that animals exposed to organophosphates may experience reproductive disorders, such as reduced fertility, abnormal development of embryos, and decreased viability of offspring (Jaga, and Dharmani, 2003). Furthermore, exposure to these pesticides can lead to behavioral changes in animals, including increased aggression, disorientation, and impaired foraging abilities.

Organochlorine pesticides, such as DDT, have also been implicated in reproductive abnormalities in animals. One notable effect is eggshell thinning, which can lead to reduced fertility and impaired hatching success in birds and other egg-laying species. The exposure to organochlorines can weaken the immune system of animals, rendering them more susceptible to infections and diseases (Rogan *et al.*, 2005). Additionally, some organochlorines have been found to have hepatotoxic effects, causing damage to the liver of animals. Moreover, these pesticides have been associated with an increased risk of cancer in animals.

Table 2: The Table Briefly Describes Toxicity Induced by Various Pesticides in Animals.

Sr. No.	Pesticides	Animals	Effects	Reference
1	Organophosphate	Birds	The deaths of approximately 9,000 birds worldwide were attributed to organophosphate exposure.	(Fleischli <i>et al.</i> 2004)
2	Methyl parathion	Male <i>roseringed parakeet</i>	Impaired testicular function was observed in male <i>roseringed parakeets</i> .	(Maitra and Mitra, 2008)
3	Endosulfan	Japanese quail	Japanese quails exhibited symptoms such as lethargy, weakness, and diarrhea after exposure to endosulfan.	(Prakash <i>et al.</i> 2009)
4	Lindane residues	Aquatic birds	Aquatic birds experienced negative effects on their eggs due to lindane residue exposure.	(Walker and Livingstone, 2013)
5	Imidacloprid	Chimpanzees and baboons in Uganda	Chimpanzees and baboons in Uganda showed congenital deformities and reproductive problems as a result of imidacloprid exposure.	(Krief <i>et al.</i> 2017)
6	Organochlorine pesticides	Endangered species, Humboldt penguins (<i>Spheniscus humboldti</i>)	Humboldt penguins were found to have organochlorine pesticides present in their blood.	(Adkesson <i>et al.</i> 2018)
7	Warfarin	Wild boars (<i>sus scrofa</i>)	Wild boars in Kerala, India, died after exposure to warfarin.	(Radhakrishnan, 2018)
8	Organo-chlorine	Chicken, cows and Goat	Higher contents of organochlorine pesticide residues were reported in the meat of chicken, cows, and goats.	(Mahanta <i>et al.</i> 2005)
9	Glyphosate	Mouse and Insects	-Promotion of carcinogenicity in mouse skin was observed after glyphosate exposure. -Reduced diversity and abundance of insects, which can have cascading effects on ecosystems	(George <i>et al.</i> 2010) (Hallmann <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
10	Carbamate pesticides	Hamster	Cytotoxic and genotoxic effects were observed in ovarian cells of hamsters.	(Soloneski <i>et al.</i> 2015)

11	Atrazine	Experimental animals	-Reproductive toxicity and delays in sexual maturation were reported in experimental animals exposed to atrazine. -Delays in sexual maturation	(Song <i>et al.</i> 2014)
12	Polychlorinated biphenyls(PCBs)	This toxic substance has been detected in birds, fish, and animals of migratory species	PCBs have been detected in birds, fish, and animals of migratory species, and their presence has been linked to population declines in migratory species.	(Pesiakova <i>et al.</i> 2017)
13	Cypermethrin	Bee, other beneficial insects, earthworms, fish, and shrimps	Cypermethrin had an impact on the nervous system of bees, other beneficial insects, earthworms, fish, and shrimps.	(Jilani <i>et al.</i> 2013)
14	Dinotefuran	Bumblebees	Around 50,000 bumblebees were killed due to dinotefuran exposure.	(Sponsler <i>et al.</i> 2019)
15	Neonicotinoid	Bee Colonies and other Pollinators	-Bee colonies experienced severe damage and mass deaths, leading to a pollination crisis. -Impairment of navigation and foraging abilities in bees and other pollinators	(Chen <i>et al.</i> 2019) (Stanley <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
16	Chlorpyrifos	Mammals	Developmental neurotoxicity in mammals, including reduced cognitive function and behavioral abnormalities	(Rauh <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
17	Carbaryl	Fishes and other aquatic animals	Acute toxicity in fish and other aquatic animals, with potential long-term effects on growth and reproduction	(Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
18	Pyrethroids	Insects	-Pyrethroids can affect the nervous system of animals, leading to symptoms such as tremors, hyperexcitability, and in severe cases, seizures. -Exposure to pyrethroids may cause behavioral alterations in animals, including increased aggression, reduced activity, and impaired learning and memory.	(Shafer <i>et al.</i> , 2005). (Roghair <i>et al.</i> , 2007).

19	Endosulphan residue	Fishes Cotton field Africa	In Africa, endosulfan residue was used by the local population to catch fish. This resulted in toxicity to other fish species. (Satyavani <i>et al.</i> 2011)
20	Expired pesticide	Fishes	In the Kara Sea, the use of expired pesticide led to alterations in pH, resulting in acute toxicity to fish. (Satyavani <i>et al.</i> 2011)

These examples highlight the potential harm that pesticides can pose to various animal species and the importance of considering their environmental impact when using such chemicals (Table 2).

Pesticides Toxicity in Humans

Pesticides can enter the human body through various routes, including inhalation of air, dust, and vapors containing pesticides, oral consumption of contaminated water and food, and dermal exposure through direct contact with pesticides (Sacramento, 2008). Once absorbed, pesticides are distributed throughout the body via the bloodstream. Pesticides are toxic to all living organisms at certain doses. When they enter the human body, they can inhibit enzymatic function and disrupt normal metabolic reactions, leading to adverse effects (Saeed *et al.*, 2017).

Indeed, there is a considerable body of research examining the impact of pesticide exposure on various chronic diseases in humans. Many studies have investigated the association between pesticide exposure and conditions such as cancer, Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, multiple sclerosis, diabetes, aging, and chronic kidney disease. However, it is worth noting that the number of studies specifically exploring the link between pesticide exposure and cardiovascular diseases is relatively limited (Mostafalou *et al.*, 2013).

Pesticides, particularly organophosphates, have been found to gradually accumulate in the human body through the consumption of pesticide-contaminated vegetables, and this accumulation has been linked to an increased risk of cancer (Miah *et al.*, 2014). Acute exposure to highly corrosive herbicides like paraquat can lead to extensive damage to multiple systems in the body and can result in pulmonary failure (Chen *et al.*, 2013). The combined exposure to multiple pesticides that share a common mechanism of action can enhance their specific toxic effects, while simultaneous exposure to different classes of pesticides may amplify the overall negative health impacts (Hayes *et al.*, 2003). Although the use of Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) has been discontinued, its long residual efficacy and accumulation in the food chain continue to impact human health. DDT has been associated with various health issues, including different types of cancer, acute and persistent damage to the nervous system, lung damage, reproductive organ injury, immune and endocrine system dysfunction, and birth defects (Thuy, 2015). These findings highlight the potential risks of pesticide exposure to human health and emphasize the importance of regulation and careful monitoring of pesticide use to protect human well-being.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), pesticide poisoning is a common method of suicide in many Asian and Latin American countries, where pesticides are often readily available and poorly controlled, especially in low and middle-income nations (Sarchiapone *et al.*, 2011). In cases of pesticide poisoning, regardless of whether it was intentional, accidental, or occupational, detoxification measures are crucial. It is relatively easy to identify poisoning when the individual knows which pesticide they were exposed to or when the symptoms are typical. However, in cases where the symptoms are generalized, poisoning may be more difficult to recognize. Therefore, in addition to implementing decontamination procedures, it is important to conduct investigations involving family members and individuals present during the contamination incident and gather relevant information about the patient's care. Prompt and appropriate management of pesticide poisoning is essential to minimize the associated health risks.

Table 3: The Table Concisely Describes Human Toxicity Resulting from Various Pesticides.

Sr. No.	Pesticide	Effects	Reference
1	Organophosphate and organochlorine	Exposure to these pesticides may increase the risk of Alzheimer's disease, particularly in individuals exposed during late life.	(Hayden <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
2	Rotenone and Paraguata	Exposure to these pesticides can disrupt dopaminergic neurons and inhibit dopamine production, potentially leading to Parkinson's disease.	(Qi <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
3	Linuron	There is a suggested association between exposure to Linuron and multiple sclerosis, a neurological disease affecting a significant number of people worldwide.	(Wheeler <i>et al.</i> 2019)
4	Chlorpyrifos	Prenatal exposure to chlorpyrifos has been linked to brain anomalies in children.	(Rauh <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
5	Pyrethroid	Exposure to pyrethroids has been associated with DNA damage in human sperm, raising concerns about potential negative effects on reproductive health.	(Jurewicz <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
6	Carbamate	Carbamate exposure has been linked to neurobehavioral disorders, an increased risk for dementia, and non-Hodgkin's lymphoma.	(Wahab <i>et al.</i> 2016)
7	Organophosphorus	Exposure to organophosphorus pesticides has been associated with cardiovascular diseases, negative effects on the male reproductive system, nervous system effects, dementia, and a possible increased risk for non-Hodgkin's lymphoma.	(Hung <i>et al.</i> , 2015) (Jamal <i>et al.</i> , 2015)

8	Neonicotinoids	Neonicotinoids may increase the expression of the enzyme aromatase, which has been implicated in breast cancer and plays a role during developmental periods.	(Caron and Beaudoin <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
9	Glyphosate-based herbicides	-These herbicides have been associated with DNA damage and endocrine disruption in human cell lines. -There is also evidence suggesting their potential to affect cytoskeleton and intracellular transport.	(Gasnier <i>et al.</i> , 2010) (Hedberg <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
10	Heptachlor and dieldrin	These pesticides have been shown to cause mitochondrial damage, oxidative stress, and induce apoptosis in cell cultures.	(Culbreth <i>et al.</i> 2012).

SUSTAINABLE ALTERNATIVES AND FUTURE PLANNING

The extensive use of pesticides has caused a considerable decline in biodiversity, disrupting ecological processes and endangering the stability of ecosystems on a global scale. Resolving this issue necessitates a shift towards sustainable agricultural practices that minimize pesticide usage while prioritizing biodiversity conservation. To achieve this, strict regulations, the promotion of alternative pest management strategies, and increased public awareness are crucial steps towards fostering a more harmonious coexistence between agriculture and biodiversity. Sustainable alternatives and future planning involve the implementation of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) as a holistic approach to reduce pesticide usage. This approach emphasizes the integration of various pest control methods, such as biological control, crop rotation, and habitat manipulation, to effectively manage pests while minimizing reliance on chemical pesticides. Additionally, promoting organic farming practices and biodiversity-friendly agriculture can significantly contribute to reducing pesticide use and preserving ecosystem health. These practices prioritize natural pest control mechanisms and strive to maintain a balanced ecosystem through the promotion of beneficial insects, diverse crop rotations, and the avoidance of synthetic chemical inputs.

Furthermore, landscape-scale conservation efforts play a vital role in creating habitat corridors and safeguarding biodiversity hotspots. By connecting fragmented habitats and protecting critical areas, these initiatives support the movement of wildlife, enhance species diversity, and contribute to overall ecosystem resilience. Investing in research and innovation is crucial for developing safer and more sustainable approaches to pest management. This includes the development of bio-pesticides, genetic pest control, precision farming techniques, and other innovative solutions that can effectively target pests while minimizing environmental impact.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a comprehensive and coordinated effort is needed to address the challenges posed by pesticide use and its impact on biodiversity. By adopting sustainable alternatives, implementing integrated pest management practices, promoting organic farming, protecting biodiversity hotspots, and fostering research

and innovation, we can pave the way for a more sustainable and harmonious coexistence between agriculture and biodiversity. We strongly advocate for the creation of pesticide-free zones by implementing comprehensive bans at the local level, particularly in urban green spaces. This is a feasible goal that can be achieved with the right regulations and support. Additionally, it is crucial to adopt alternative approaches to the current conventional model of food production. New agricultural policies should prioritize sustainable development and the protection of consumers' health.

While transitioning to a new and safer agricultural model may present challenges, it is a necessary step forward. It requires innovation, collaboration, and a collective commitment to creating a cleaner and more sustainable environment. By reducing reliance on pesticides and embracing alternative practices, we can promote the well-being of both ecosystems and human health.

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